

Country Snapshot

Infrastructure for Returns /Readmission from EU Member States to Morocco

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1. Introduction

This snapshot report on the case of Morocco is part of Work Package 3 (WP3). WP3 is designed to study how return migration governance is implemented, including how different actors collaborate or oppose each other, and what discrepancies arise and persist in their daily management of return migration. In doing so, we utilise the Return Migration Infrastructures (RMI) concept. RMIs consist of various state and non-state actors, the relationships between these actors, their actions, and the technologies/materialities that together operationalise return migration governance. Compared to other country dossiers, this report relies less on qualitative research, such as interviews and observations, and more on desk research and document analysis. In this WP, we distinguish three return types: assisted returns, forced removals, and push-backs. This report predominantly focuses on the first.

In recent years, return migration has become a crucial aspect of European migration policies. Located along the two main routes for irregular migration to Europe, Morocco has served – since the end of the last century - as a transit hub for migrants travelling via the Western Mediterranean route, connecting Morocco with the Spanish mainland, the Balearic Islands, and the Moroccan enclaves of Ceuta and Melilla. Additionally, it plays a role in the Western African Atlantic route, which links the coasts of West African countries to the Canary Islands.

Morocco's geographical importance requires increased border control, leading to ongoing arrests and pushbacks by national authorities. Morocco aims to facilitate the return of migrants on its territory to their home countries while safeguarding their rights, and also bears the responsibility to manage the repatriation of its migrants from Europe under the best possible conditions, regardless of the circumstances surrounding such returns.

Although Morocco has implemented relatively advanced migration policies, such as the "New Immigration Policy" of 2013 and the National Strategy for Immigration and Asylum (SNIA, in French), which mainly focus on foreigners, it faces a significant internal challenge: receiving and integrating its own returning migrants. Addressing this challenge requires strengthening reception infrastructure, especially in terms of healthcare access, and promoting active collaboration between public authorities, civil society, and relevant international organisations.

2. Policies towards Moroccan's Abroad and Their Return

Before moving to discuss forced removals or assisted return of Morocco's from European countries, it is necessary to note that Moroccan authorities are interested in carrying a set of programs and initiatives to encourage the return (permanent or temporary) of Moroccans Residing Abroad (MRA). However, no law or specific structure is dedicated to the reception of returned migrants. More recently, a report on a "New Development Model" (NMD) - which was supposed, under the inspiration of the King, to cover all economic and social sectors in Morocco, between 2019 and 2035, allowing the country to achieve an annual growth rate of 6.5%, published in May 2021, devoted a chapter to MRA, considering their potential contribution as an important factor in reviving the economy in Morocco.¹ So, the NDM emphasizes the prominent role of the MRA, who represent a strength and a valuable asset in the country's development process. In this regard, the commission that was responsible for developing this model reiterates the importance of the implementation of the constitutional provisions for a better representation of the diaspora, particularly through the strengthening of the Council for the Moroccan Community Residing Abroad. It also calls for emphasis to be placed on the implementation of renewed policies adapted to the needs and expectations of this important segment of the Moroccan population and to the protection of its interests with the countries of residence. the prevailing official discourse, as well as the existence of public structures, such as the Hassan II Foundation or the Consultative Council of Moroccans Living Abroad (CCME, in French).

The government department in charge of the Moroccans abroad indicate a strong interest in this community. This in particular because of their contribution through the remittances of savings to the benefit of the country's economy² as well as because of the political fallout of their presence outside Morocco, coupled with the fact that emigration continues to have a positive influence on the domestic labour market, given the high unemployment rate.³

¹ See https://www.csmd.ma/documents/CSMD_Report_EN.pdf. The NMD project also considers it essential to mobilize Moroccans of the World for the development of scientific research, R&D, and innovation activities, given the expertise acquired by the diaspora in this area. Achieving this objective depends on several prerequisites, including the structuring of the scientific research ecosystem and its alignment with the country's strategic priorities, through clearly defined national programs with transparent modes of governance and regular monitoring and evaluation.

² With an amount of 117.7 billion dirhams (about 11 billion euros), transfers from MREs represent 7.7% of the national GDP in 2024. This calculation is based on a nominal GDP estimated at 1,530 billion dirhams for the year 2024, reflecting an economic growth of 3.1% compared to 2023. See Medi24. <https://medias24.com/> February 6, 2025. (In French).

³ It should be noted that The National Agency for the Promotion of Employment and Skills (ANAPEC) does not offer services that are specifically designed for return migrants, but still involve in reintegration indirectly. Returnees may benefit from the same services provided by this public agency to all other Moroccans looking for work. Therefore, the path of a user in this employment agency begins with an interview to assess their needs and define their potential path, which may lead to salaried employment, business creation, or the establishment of an income-generating activity. To strengthen the skills of its users and support them in

Considered a constitutional body, the Consultative Council of Moroccans Living Abroad (CCME, in French) is responsible, in particular, for proposing orientations for public policies to ensure that Moroccans residing abroad maintain close ties to their Moroccan identity. Measures aimed at guaranteeing their rights and preserving their interests, as well as contributing to the human and sustainable development of their country of origin and its progress. The fact is that this Council, despite all its proclamations about defending the rights of Moroccan migrants in all the countries where they are, has never been interested in the issue of those who have returned among them. We have not found any document to this effect, produced in recent years by this body.

There is no special infrastructure for Moroccan returnees at the borders (ports and airports) of the country, as well as no specific monitoring. Moroccan border police do not question Moroccans leaving their country about the reasons for their departure or their final destination. Also, they do not question them at the time of their return about the reason for this return. It only carries out an investigation/research on them if the return is motivated by an expulsion linked to a conviction or suspicion of committing a crime or offense abroad. These practices can be attributed to two reasons. First is the desire not to stigmatize a group of people already significantly affected by their forced return, as well as the refusal to highlight the fact that Moroccans are forced to return to Morocco or expelled from the countries where they were. Second is the absence of means to ensure their monitoring, or the material and legal difficulties in carrying out this. This can be attributed to that Morocco is a country with a low per capita income, where the state's financial resources are limited.

3. Trends of Moroccan returns from the EU

The dynamics of return and readmission between the European Union (EU) and Morocco reveal complex interactions between migration governance policies and their practical implementation.

The enforcement of immigration law statistics provides data on third-country citizens who were ordered to leave various European countries and the number of those who returned after the order. The number of return orders issued to Moroccan citizens in 2023 (Table 1) shows significant differences in how return orders are enforced for Moroccan citizens across EU member states and related countries. Of the 35,160 Moroccan nationals ordered to leave, only 7.9% complied, indicating a low overall return rate. EU Member States made up most of these cases, with 34,985 orders issued and a similar return rate of 7.8%. The enforcement of return orders varies greatly between countries, with Denmark (50%) and Croatia (42.2%) showing higher compliance rates, probably due to effective return procedures. In contrast, countries like Belgium (1.2%) and Austria (1.1%) have notably low return rates (Eurostat 2025). Germany issued 925 return orders to Moroccan citizens, with 155 returns successfully carried out, resulting in a return rate of 16.8%. The Netherlands issued 1,325 orders, with 200 returns, yielding a return rate of 15.1%. France issued the highest number of orders at 10,570, with 720 returns, achieving a return rate of 6.8%. Spain issued 2,670 orders and successfully returned 640 individuals, corresponding to a return rate of 24.0%. Sweden, with 185 orders, recorded 75 returns, representing a return rate of 40.5% (Eurostat 2025).

possible retraining, ANAPEC offers a range of professional training, face-to-face or remote, based on partnerships with (See <https://anapec.ma/home-page-01/mobilite-internationale/migration-de-retour>.)

Table 1: Moroccan citizens who returned from EU member states, following an order to leave in 2023

Country	Number of persons ordered to leave	Number of returned following an order to leave	Percentage
Belgium	4,815	60	1.2
Bulgaria	2,080	75	3.6
Czechia	100	20	20.0
Denmark	40	20	50.0
Germany	925	155	16.8
Estonia	0	0	-
Ireland	0	0	-
Greece	285	15	5.3
Spain	2,670	640	24.0
France	10,570	720	6.8
Croatia	320	135	42.2
Italy	5,315	400	7.5
Cyprus	5	0	0.0
Latvia	0	0	-
Lithuania	0	0	-
Luxembourg	80	5	6.3
Hungary	70	0	0.0
Malta	5	0	0.0
Netherlands	1,325	200	15.1
Austria	5,745	65	1.1
Poland	45	15	33.3
Portugal	60	10	16.7
Romania	195	75	38.5
Slovenia	40	5	12.5
Slovakia	55	10	18.2
Finland	55	15	27.3
Sweden	185	75	40.5
Liechtenstein	0	0	-
Norway	30	5	16.7
Switzerland	145	60	41.4

Montenegro	0	0	-
Total	35,160	2780	7.9
Sub-Total (EU Countries)	34,985	2715	7.8

Source: Eurostat. 2025.

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirtn1_custom_10367311/default/table?lang=en. Last updated 27.06.2025. Accessed 03.07.2025

Graph 1: Quarterly data of Moroccan returnees following an order to leave, Q2-2022 to Q3-2024

Source: Eurostat 2025a. Quarterly Statistics. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title>Returns_of_irregular_migrants_-_quarterly_statistics. 10 June 2025. Accessed 03.07.2025

Quarterly data on the return of Moroccan citizens following an order to leave the territory of EU countries, for the period 2022-2024 (Graph 1), highlight fluctuations in the number of returns. These variations are likely due to differing levels of cooperation between these countries and Moroccan authorities in identifying nationals awaiting deportation—an essential step in the return process. However, the levels of cooperation in this regard are closely tied to the quality of diplomatic and political relations between Morocco and certain European governments, particularly Germany, France, and Spain. Notably, when these three countries adopted favourable positions towards Morocco regarding the so-called Ex-Spanish Sahara issue—Spain in 2022, Germany in 2023, and France in 2024—cooperation with them became smoother, including in matters related to return migration. The trend showed a gradual increase until early 2023, followed by a drop in the second quarter of 2023. There was a sharp recovery in the third quarter of 2023, followed by continued growth in early 2024, with the peak in the first quarter of 2024 exceeding 1,000 returns. According to Eurostat, “among non-

EU citizens ordered to leave the territory of an EU country in this period, Moroccan and Algerian citizens had the largest share of the total, each with 7%” (EC 2024).

Table 2: Detections of Illegal Border Crossings (IBC) at the EU’s external borders and Return decisions - 2015-2022. Data concerning Moroccans

Year	Detections of illegal border crossings	Return decisions	Including Effective returns	Forced returns
2015	12,966	22,360	8,158	7,017
2016	6,836	22,437	8,672	6,901
2017	11,279	22,028	10,047	8,936
2018	13,269	19,023	10,893	10,010
2019	8,020	23,553	2,780	9,074
2020	17,594	34 633	2,780	2,276
2021	16,482	34,633	2,621	1,895
2022	14,764	39,163	2,850	2,194
Total	101,210	217,830	48,801	48,303

Source: Frontex. Data on returnees, 2015-2022. www.frontex.org

4. The bilateral readmission agreement and mobility partnerships

Morocco has entered into multiple readmission agreements and partnerships with European countries. For Morocco, the readmission agreement(s) are not an end in themselves but part of a broader strategy to strengthen bilateral cooperation with European states. Main features of bilateral agreements can be summarized as follows:

France

- Exchange of letters agreement (EL), 1983-1993 : This agreement established a framework to facilitate the residence and employment of nationals from both countries. It granted Moroccan nationals in France and French nationals in Morocco long-term residence permits and work authorizations, enhancing cooperation on mobility and integration (France-Maroc. 1994)
- Police/security agreement (CP), May 1, 2001 (Maroc-France. 2022) : A police cooperation agreement aimed at strengthening collaboration on security issues, including combating irregular migration and facilitating the readmission of individuals in irregular situations.
- Declaration of Understanding, December 7, 2020: This specific agreement addresses the readmission and protection of unaccompanied minors, ensuring mechanisms for their safe return and reintegration in Morocco (Maroc diplomatique. 2020).

Spain

- Provisional Agreement (AP), February 13, 1992 (The Rights Angle 2013): This agreement covers the readmission of irregular migrants, including third-country nationals, and aims to reinforce bilateral cooperation in managing migration flows and combating irregular

migration. It was partially implemented in 2004. October 21, 2012 (Boletín Oficial del Estado (BOE). 2012) is the full enforcement of the 1992 agreement, solidifying its provisions.

- Memorandum of understanding, December 23, 2003: Focused on the readmission of unaccompanied minors, this agreement ensures their safe return to Morocco under conditions guaranteeing post-return assistance, training, and reintegration support.
- Memorandum of understanding (Boletín Oficial del Estado (BOE). 2013), March 6, 2007: A comprehensive readmission agreement aimed to replace the 2003 agreement (ME), but it has yet to enter into force.
- Police cooperation agreement (Boletín Oficial del Estado (BOE). 2012), May 20, 2012: Established cross-border police cooperation to combat terrorism, organized crime, irregular migration, human trafficking, and drug and arms smuggling through Police Cooperation Centers in Algeciras and Tangier.

Belgium

- 21/10/1993 (ME S): The first readmission agreement between Belgium and Morocco, addressing the process of return of irregular Moroccan nationals.
- 22/04/2016 (ME S) (Moniteur Belge. 2020): Cooperation agreement to combat organized crime and terrorism, addressing areas such as drug trafficking, human trafficking, and cybercrime. This agreement strengthens bilateral collaboration through information exchange, logistical and technical assistance, and mechanisms for more effective prevention and prosecution.
- 15/04/2024 (ME S) (Ministère des Affaires Étrangères du Maroc. 2023): A joint declaration that aims to enhance migration management between the two countries.

The Netherlands

- Morocco and the Netherlands, signed on July 8, 2021, a Joint Action Plan to strengthen bilateral cooperation. In the field of migration, the two parties agreed to strengthen their cooperation, in particular through the establishment of a cooperation committee and To bring together the Moroccan community established in the Netherlands and the Dutch community established in Morocco in favor of strengthening cultural cooperation. But there is no explicit reference in this text to readmission (Kingdom of Morocco. 2021).

Italy

- Rabat, July 27, 1998 (S): Conclusion of an agreement between the Government of the Italian Republic and the Government of the Kingdom of Morocco on the deportation of nationals from both countries and on transit for removal.

Portugal

- October 22, 2004 Agreement (V): A border and migration management agreement that emphasizes practical measures to facilitate cooperation, including managing irregular migration and promoting lawful migration practices.

Germany

- 01/06/1998 (V) (Bundesgesetzblatt (BGBl). 1998): protocol between Germany and Morocco establishes procedures for identifying Moroccan nationals in Germany and issuing travel documents for their repatriation, particularly for those in irregular situations. It ensures compliance with international obligations, protects personal data, and facilitates collaboration between the two countries' authorities.

Austria

- 28/02/2023 (S) (Austrian Federal Ministry for European and International Affairs. 2022): A joint declaration reaffirming Austria and Morocco's shared commitment to tackle irregular migration, promote voluntary returns, and support reintegration.

United Kingdom

- September 24, 2011 Agreement (ME): Focused on the readmission of irregular Moroccan migrants, this agreement also encompasses broader cooperation in migration governance and addressing irregular flows effectively.

These agreements are often asymmetrical, reflecting power imbalances. European countries, particularly those within the European Union, have significant leverage due to their economic power, institutional capacity, and control over critical incentives such as financial aid, trade agreements, and visa facilitation, often prioritizing their migration control goals over Morocco's development needs.

5. Negotiations with the EU, Morocco's priorities, and Funding

Euro-Mediterranean Agreement established an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Kingdom of Morocco, of the other part. The EU-Morocco Association Agreement (Article 71) (European Union. 2000) entered into force in 2000 and created a Free Trade Area between the EU and Morocco. In this agreement, Morocco has committed to the reintegration of irregular migrants. However, this commitment operates within a framework that emphasizes Morocco's sovereignty and strategic priorities. The EU-Morocco Mobility Partnership, signed in 2013 and involving nine EU Member States (France, Germany, Sweden, the Netherlands, Spain, Italy, Belgium, Portugal, and the UK), aims to foster closer alignment of Moroccan and EU migration policies. The partnership seeks to maximize the benefits of migration for both sides while addressing irregular migration. Despite this collaboration, significant points of contention remain, particularly regarding the proposed EU readmission agreement, which Morocco views as problematic (Council of European Union, 2013)).

The proposed EU readmission agreement's scope includes third-country nationals and stateless individuals who transited through Morocco. Morocco opposes this expansion, asserting that readmission obligations should apply strictly to Moroccan nationals. This stance reflects Morocco's effort to balance its international commitments with the protection of its sovereignty and the rights of migrants.

According to interviewed informants, Morocco has articulated several conditions during negotiations with the EU, underscoring its priorities:

- **Limiting Readmission to Moroccan Nationals:** Morocco insists that readmission should exclusively involve its citizens, rejecting the inclusion of third-country nationals and stateless individuals.
- **Ensuring Formal Evidence:** Identification of Moroccan nationals must be based on tangible and formal documentation to avoid wrongful deportations.
- **Compliance with Bilateral Agreements:** Any readmission must adhere to existing bilateral agreements, and expulsion decisions must be subject to judicial oversight.

- **Individual Repatriations:** Repatriations should be conducted on an individual basis using regular flights, ensuring dignity and procedural fairness.
- **Financial and Technical Support:** Morocco demands EU assistance to establish robust reintegration programs for returnees.
- **Visa Facilitation Agreements:** Morocco links cooperation on readmission to reciprocal visa facilitation measures, enhancing mobility for its citizens.
- **Regional Cooperation:** Morocco advocates for similar agreements with neighboring Mediterranean and Sub-Saharan countries, under frameworks like the Cotonou Agreement, to create a regional approach to migration management.

This specific agreement often intersects with other critical issues, such as 1) Security, because migration management often ties into broader counter-terrorism and border security initiatives. 2) Energy and Trade as Morocco uses its position in readmission negotiations to secure trade and energy agreements that benefit its economy, and 3) Geopolitical Partnerships because readmission cooperation often leads to stronger political ties and access to EU financial and technical resources.

Morocco's cooperation on readmission reflects the principle of reciprocity, where the level of commitment depends on the broader alignment of interests between Morocco and the EU. Tangible benefits, such as financial support, visa facilitation, and strategic partnerships, appear to be key incentive factors for Morocco to engage in migration-related agreements. These agreements often mirror asymmetric power dynamics, with Morocco utilising its geopolitical influence, especially in regions like the Maghreb and the Sahel, which experience considerable political and security unrest, to bolster its negotiating stance. Considering the EU's economic and political heft, Morocco aims to secure concessions that serve its national interests and priorities, thus engaging in bilateral readmission agreements and mobility partnerships with various EU countries and the UK.

The EU supports the return and reintegration of migrants via the Emergency Trust Fund - North Africa Window. The FFU-NoA intervenes in Morocco's seven national and seven regional programs. The national and regional programs implemented work on multiple facets of migration through support for border management, the regionalization of migration policies, the fight against criminal networks exploiting migration, the focus on migrants in transit in Morocco, and direct assistance to migrants. On this last point, the FFU-NoA intervenes in Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Libya, and Egypt via the EU-IOM North Africa Joint Initiative and through the Facility for the Protection and Reintegration of Migrants in North Africa, with a budget of €10 million aimed at the reintegration of nationals of these States. The EU-IOM North Africa Joint Initiative, for its part, assists in the return and reintegration of sub-Saharan and Horn of Africa migrants in transit through these states. IOM provides return assistance and reintegration assistance in Morocco for European national schemes and within the framework of the Facility for the Protection of Migrants and Reintegration in North Africa. This project, funded by the Emergency Trust Fund - North Africa Window (the FFU-NoA), offers individual, collective, or community reintegration assistance depending on the eligibility criteria. IOM's support to assisted returns will be discussed below.

6. IOM programs about assisting the returned Moroccans

IOM implements the AVRR in close collaboration with the Moroccan government, particularly the Ministry of Home Affairs, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, African Cooperation, Moroccans Living Abroad, and the diplomatic missions of the countries of origin or host of assisted migrants. This programme supports the Moroccan Government's strategies in migration

management. In this regard, the IOM assists in establishing effective migration policies in Morocco by participating in, for example, the steering committees and subcommittees of the National Immigration and Asylum Strategy (SNIA), which includes the component of “return migration” in cross-functional programmes. The IOM has also developed a vast network of partnerships with international organizations active in Morocco, NGO’s - including the Association for the Fight against AIDS (ALCS), the Association Tissaghnaasse for Culture and Development (ASTICUDE), the Bayti Association, the Maroc Solidarité-Médico-Social Association (MS2), the Moroccan Family Planning Association (AMPF), etc- and some specialists in the legal, medical or research fields. (IOM, 2022)

IOM has sought to establish a Working and Reintegration Group (WRG) to facilitate technical coordination between associative bodies and international cooperation working on the assistance, protection, and reintegration of returned Moroccans. The main objective of the WRG is to bring all actors together to work in synergy to best meet the expectations and needs of the target population while ensuring a coordinated approach to reintegration assistance that efficiently uses available resources, avoids duplication of assistance, ensures sustainable reintegration, and facilitates exchanges of good practices and lessons learned. During 2022, IOM also organized several national and regional workshops on the theme of return and reintegration, which brought together and brought together various institutional actors, development agencies, and civil society actors from Morocco and the MENA region. These workshops provided an opportunity to reflect on the ecosystem of existing reintegration services in the Moroccan context and how the actors concerned can participate in strengthening this ecosystem for sustainable reintegration.

IOM Morocco is also implementing the ORION project, which offers community-based assistance led by mentors, thus contributing to the sustainable reintegration of returning migrants. The mentors advise them on their reintegration project by providing knowledge of the field and directing them to the appropriate services. In addition, with funding from IOM's Development Fund, IOM Morocco has launched the project "Mobilization of the Diaspora for the Development of Agroecology in Morocco," which plans to support returned Moroccans in the implementation of projects related to the field of agroecology. It brings together a community of practitioners and offers training and publications related to the themes of reintegration.

According to the IOM, assistance to Moroccans returning is guided by the principles of the sustainable reintegration approach, developed by the organisation in 2017. The ultimate objective of this approach is to comprehensively address the economic, social, and psychosocial needs of the beneficiaries while considering the community context to which they return. Assistance with the reintegration of returning Moroccans is a process that begins, for IOM, before return through coordination with host country missions, organisation of virtual sessions with potential returnees, exchange of information on the economic and social context in Morocco, study of the feasibility of reintegration plans developed by the missions of the host countries, and, finally, family members' research.

According to the IOM, in 2022, approximately 639 Moroccans "voluntarily returned" to Morocco. The number of returns increased substantially that year due to the socio-economic crisis in Europe following the COVID-19 pandemic and events after the war in Ukraine, which began in February. During the same year, 216 returnees (including 193 men, 18 women, two girls, and three boys, seven of whom were in a situation of increased vulnerability) received reintegration assistance. Seventy-six per cent of Moroccans assisted in 2022 were aged between 18 and 39 years, with 9% being women and 83% having spent less than 12 months abroad before requesting assisted voluntary return. (IOM 2022). Additionally, return requests from non-EU countries such as Turkey and Tunisia increased significantly.

In 2022, IOM assisted returning Moroccans with different types of interventions:

- Economic assistance, through the payment of cash assistance after return to meet the most urgent needs (in 2022, 183 people benefited from this assistance), and the establishment of Income-generating activities (IGAs) to ensure a stable and sustainable income (in 2022, IOM financed 154 IGAs).
- Vocational training to enable returnees to meet the requirements of the labor market (to this end, IOM organized 2 training sessions on entrepreneurship and marketing for 17 beneficiaries).
- The networking and implementation of collective projects, bringing together at least two returnees.
- Social assistance, through rent and temporary housing support, payment of school fees, and aid to facilitate access to health and legal services. At this level, in 2022, 11 returned Moroccans received housing assistance, 30 received support from legal services to obtain identity documents or other documents, 12 were assisted to obtain legal status (Auto-entrepreneur card/cooperative status) and 27 were referred to various organizations for training or material support (including the German Chamber of Commerce and Industry (AHK), the youth platforms of the National Initiative for Human Development (INDH, a public initiative to combat poverty launched in 2005 on the instruction of the king), and to the National Union of Women in Morocco (UNFM).

7. International Implementing Actors in Return and Returning Infrastructure

Besides IOM, there are also intermediaries and implementing actors. Caritas International Belgium (CIB) is an operator of the Belgian national return and reintegration scheme. As such, it participates in reintegration activities in Morocco with the support of a local partner: the Orient-Occident Foundation. Based in Rabat, and with integration/reintegration bodies in Fez, Meknes, Rabat, Casablanca, Tangier, and Oujda, this foundation offers psychosocial support to returned migrants and supports them in the development of reintegration plans. The follow-up of reintegration projects is carried out according to individual needs and through regular contacts. Although the Orient-Occident Foundation is present in the majority of major Moroccan cities, the geographical distance of the returned migrants, who resettle in often isolated areas, can be a difficulty for the proper implementation of the support. CIB and the Orient-Occident Foundation (like ANAPEC) highlight the difficulty for returnees to take part in training in the absence of income to support themselves. Indeed, as soon as they return, the priority of the latter is often focused on launching an income-generating activity that puts training offers in the background. They also highlight the fact that some returnees do not use national aid systems, either because they are unaware of their existence or sometimes because of a certain apprehension of the administration. This emerged clearly during the field research we conducted in 2008 (MIREM, 2008) on Moroccan returnees, many of whom lived in rural areas, far from the cities where reception structures or associations are located. Some of them also viewed the Moroccan administration—and sometimes certain international organizations, such as the IOM—as complicit with the European authorities that had sent them back. Including when the return was voluntary.

CEFA (an Italian NGO) is a partner in three national reintegration programs in Morocco, respectively since 2012 for Italy, since 2016 for France, and since 2018 for Germany. These programs all offer assistance for economic reintegration, but CEFA accompanies returning migrants in their administrative procedures with public aid organizations such as RAMED (Moroccan social coverage) or ANAPEC if the profiles match. CEFA underlines the difficulty

for returnees to enroll in specific trainings, on the one hand, because the trainings generally require a minimum number of participants which is not always reached, as returns are not constant, and, on the other hand, the beneficiaries have to support themselves, which constitutes an additional and important obstacle, limiting their possible participation to the fees of trainings. CEFA has operated in Morocco in 12 regions/cities, with financial EU support, for 34 months (from February 2018 to November 2020). Its beneficiaries were migrants and vulnerable refugees without professional competencies. Its main important partners were the Moroccan public organization helping disadvantaged populations, "Entraide Nationale", the IOM, and the UNHCR.

Alongside these actors, one should mention the contributions of the embassies of Norway, Belgium, and the Netherlands in Morocco, as well as those of the French Development Agency. Also noteworthy are the contributions of Spanish associations in the northern regions of Morocco, as well as that of the Franco-Moroccan association, Migration and Development, which was created in 1986, by some Moroccan migrants living in France, to carry out development actions in the villages of their region of origin, the Moroccan Atlas and Anti-Atlas.

Box: An example of collaboration between GIZ and Moroccan NGO's RNO - Integration Project Towards a better (re)integration of Moroccan returnees and sub-Saharan immigrants in Morocco

A Returnees Program - "Returning to New Opportunities"/RNO. January 2018/March 2020.

Target group: The direct target group was Moroccan returnees and sub-Saharan immigrants present on Moroccan territory. Priority would be given to young people between the ages of 15 and 40 and women, who represent a particularly vulnerable group.

Partners: To carry out this project, DVV International had to collaborate with three Universities for All (UPT) in Tetouan, Ksar El Kébir (in the northern part of Morocco), and Fez, with the REMADAV (Moroccan Network for Development and Lifelong Learning) in Tangier, Oujda, Fez, Agadir, and Taroudant, and with local associations in other cities like Errachidia, Oued-Zem, Rabat, and Casablanca.

This project, initiated by the German NGO Deutscher Volkshochschul-Verband eV (DVV) International and financially supported by the German Cooperation Agency GIZ, was based on Morocco's migratory context. The Returning to New Opportunities programme was intended to be part of the National Strategy for Immigration and Asylum and was to be carried out in consultation with the Ministry Delegate for Migration Affairs and the National Commission for the Integration and Regularization of Migrants. The project also provided for close collaboration with other German cooperation projects, in particular the GIZ programs, and projects of Moroccan partners such as the General Confederation of Moroccan Enterprises (CGEM), to offer the target groups a program with practical and coherent content and important synergy effects.

In March 2020, the month during which the COVID-19 crisis began, with the total closure of all Moroccan borders, 1,500 people benefited from the services of the RNO project, including 300 Moroccans returned/repatriated.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

Beyond the institutional and political issues that may arise in the process of returning migrants invited to return home, from the moment the decision to return is taken until they arrive in Morocco, several problems/difficulties of both an individual and general nature can make the return and integration of Moroccan migrants living abroad difficult, including

- 1) The geographical dispersion of returnees in the countries where they lived abroad, as well as their dispersion in terms of the places where they settle after their return to Morocco, makes communication with them very difficult.
- 2) They do not return to their families because of the feeling of a sort of shame that they may have following the failure of their migratory experience. This can lead to losing all contact with them, due to the difficulty in obtaining their addresses.
- 3) The limited trust of actual returnees, as well as potential returnees, vis-à-vis the administrative authorities, both in the countries from which they return and in Morocco.
- 4) The low level of education of returnees, which also represents a serious factor limiting the chances of successful integration at the time of return. This same factor also makes formal/conventional communication with them complicated

Some relevant recommendations can be formulated as follows:

Establishment of a system for collecting and cross-checking data concerning returns

There has always been a significant amount of uncertainty, and it still remains, regarding the number of Moroccans who have returned, the reasons for their return, the countries from which they came, and the regions where they settled after re-entering Morocco. The same lack of clarity applies to their socio-professional data—age, gender, educational level, and work experience. Determining all these elements beforehand within a population facing financial and social hardships would be very challenging. Nevertheless, an effective initial step towards better understanding this issue would be to establish a shared database between the countries from which migrants return and the Moroccan authorities.

Currently, it is challenging for Moroccan border police to accurately identify which Moroccan citizens cross the country's borders. Additionally, it would be more feasible for organisations like the IOM, Frontex, or the UNHCR to share less sensitive information with their partners in Morocco. These same international bodies might also consider offering relevant incentives to encourage returned migrants to disclose their status once their return has been confirmed.

Need for social and psychological support.

If it is legally challenging for Moroccan public authorities to prioritise Moroccans who have returned from certain public services (such as education, vocational training, access to health, or employment), it would be beneficial to provide them with adequate social and psychological support, considering the reasons and circumstances of their return. From this perspective, particular attention could be given to mental health services. However, the fact remains that Morocco had 343 psychiatrists in 2023, distributed across both private and public sectors, which amounts to roughly one psychiatrist per nearly 107,000 people inhabitants (Ministère de la Santé du Maroc. 2023). This is in addition to the observation that there are only less than 29,000 doctors in Morocco, all specialties combined, which corresponds to fewer than 8 doctors per 10,000 inhabitants (Ministère de la Santé du Maroc. 2022).

Need to organize communication campaigns aimed at returnees

It would also be very useful to run communication campaigns targeting Moroccan returnees and the Moroccan public in general to inform them about the professional training options available, as well as potential employment pathways or organisations that facilitate employment access.

Encourage society's associations to take an interest in the subject of support for returnees.

Many returnees have more confidence in civil society associations than in the administrative staff. Return policies must recognise that a forced return, which happens under conditions where the rights and dignity of the individual are not respected, leads to a break in the morale of the migrant. This makes it difficult for them to reintegrate into their society of origin and, consequently, often pushes them to find all means to migrate again, either to the country from which they were deported or elsewhere. They then risk entering a vicious cycle that could lead to delinquency or violent actions, both at home and abroad.

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